

Supporting Information

**Comparative Analysis of Local and Nonlocal Elasticity Theories at the
Nanoscale via FEM and MD Simulations**

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--- MD — TP kernel

(a) sharp crack, $\tau = 4$

(b) blunt crack, $\tau = 4$

(c) sharp crack, $\tau = 6$

(d) blunt crack, $\tau = 6$

(e) sharp crack, $\tau = 7$

(f) blunt crack, $\tau = 7$

(g) sharp crack, $\tau = 8$

(h) blunt crack, $\tau = 8$

Fig. S1. Final crack shape from non-local elasticity with the TP kernel and $\xi = 0.75$ compared to MD results (horizontal and vertical axes representing x and y coordinates in \AA , respectively)

--- MD — Mod. kernel

(a) sharp crack, $\tau = 3$

(b) blunt crack, $\tau = 3$

(c) sharp crack, $\tau = 4$

(d) blunt crack, $\tau = 4$

(e) sharp crack, $\tau = 5$

(f) blunt crack, $\tau = 5$

(g) sharp crack, $\tau = 6$

(h) blunt crack, $\tau = 6$

Fig. S2. Final crack shape from non-local elasticity with the modified kernel and $\xi = 0.75$ compared to MD results (horizontal and vertical axes representing x and y coordinates in \AA , respectively)

Fig. S3. Final crack shape from non-local elasticity with the CTP kernel and $\xi = 0.75$ compared to MD results (horizontal and vertical axes representing x and y coordinates in Å, respectively)